

The Effect of Motivation on Human Resource Performance

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Abstract: This study aims to determine the influence of the level of motivation on performance in the Inspectorate General (ITJEN) is the Government Internal Supervision Apparatus (APIP) within the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology (Kemendikbudristek).

ITJEN Kemendikbudristek has a vital role in realizing the quality and accountable management of state university (PTN) governance. For this reason, it is essential to conduct research related to the audit performance produced by ITJEN and how the level of motivation affects what has a causality relationship with the resulting audit performance. Based on the results of research and discussion, it can be concluded that the level of motivation and employee performance is not optimal. As for statistical analysis, it is known that the level of motivation has a positive and significant influence in carrying out its role in the organization.

Keywords: Motivation, Human Resource Performance, Motivation, ITJEN.

1. INTRODUCTION

Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 60 of 2008 concerning the Government Internal Control System. ITJEN is functionally the government's internal supervision apparatus. The existence of ITJEN's performance is expected to create adequate confidence for the achievement of the Ministry of Education and Culture goals.

The high low performance of ITJEN is a measure related to the ability to run the Government's Internal Control System, which will result in the emergence of the potential for the implementation of disorderly, uncontrolled, inefficient, and ineffective governance.

The low performance of ITJEN will result in problems related to the misuse of state resource utilization. Amid the efforts of the Ministry of Education and Culture in improving the quality of education with the implementation of Merdeka Belajar Kampus Merdeka (MBKM), the problem of implementing orderly, controlled, efficient, and effective governance in achieving goals is a problem that is very much to be avoided. These problems will hinder efforts to improve the nation's competitiveness.

Theoretically, the high and low performance will be determined significantly by employees' willingness to carry out their roles. The level of motivation of employees measures the level of readiness. A high level of reason, which can create a competitive advantage for the organization, is fundamental (Blumberg and Pringle 1982; Luthan 2006; Robbins and Coulter 2016; McShane and Glinow 2018; Colquitt, Lepine and Wesson 2018; Robbins and Judge 2017).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Motivation is an impulse that comes from within the individual that arises due to shortcomings, needs, and desires to direct the direction of the individual's actions and behavior to meet the needs of both physical and psychic. Motivation refers to how a person's efforts are energized, directed, and sustained towards achieving a goal. (Robbins and Coulter 2016, 96).

This definition has three critical elements of energy, direction, and perseverance. The energy element is a measure of intensity or impulse. A motivated person shows effort and works hard. However, the quality of that effort must also be considered. A high level of activity does not necessarily lead to the performance of profitable work unless the action is channeled in a direction that benefits the organization. A directed and consistent business with the organization's goals is the type of business we want from our employees. Finally, motivation includes the dimension of perseverance. We want employees to be diligent in their efforts to achieve these goals.

Motivation represents the forces within a person that affect their direction, Intensity, and persistence of behavior (Colquitt, Lepine, and Wesson 2018, 163). Motivation represents a force in a person that affects his direction—intensity and persistence of behavior. Motivation refers to the details in a person that influences voluntary behavior's direction, passion, and perseverance. Motivated employees are willing to exert a certain level of effort (intensity) for a certain period (persistence) towards a specific goal (direction). Motivation is one of the four essential drivers of individual behavior and performance.

Motivation refers to the forces within a person that affects the direction, intensity, and persistence of voluntary behavior. Motivated employees are willing to exert a particular level of effort (power), for a certain amount of time (industry), toward a specific goal (direction). Motivation is one of the four essential drivers of individual behavior and performance (McShane and Glinow 2018, 121).

These days, executives discuss employee motivation; they also tend to express employee engagement. Although its definition is debatable, we define worker involvement as the individual's emotional and cognitive (logical) motivation, precisely the focused, intense, persistent effort and aim towards work-related objectives. It is emotional involvement in, commitment, and satisfaction with work.

Employee engagement also includes a high level of absorption in work and the experience of focusing intensely on a task with limited awareness of events outside of that job. Finally, employee engagement is often described as **self-efficacy**, the belief that you have the ability, clarity of roles, and resources to get the job done. Employee engagement is on the minds of many business leaders because of the evidence that it predicts the performance of employees and work units. Employee engagement is on the minds of many business leaders because of the evidence that it expects the performance of employees and work units. Meanwhile, according to Robbins (1999:50), translated by J.Winardi,

"The willingness to carry out high efforts for organizational purposes, which are conditioned by the ability of such efforts to meet the needs of a particular individual."

According to Stanford (2000:93), translated by Mangkunegara:

"Motivation is a concept that we use to describe the impulses that arise in or from a person or individual that move and direct behavior."

An organization not only expects all its employees to be capable, capable, and skilled, but most importantly, they are willing to work hard and want to achieve optimal work results. Employees' abilities, abilities, and skills are meaningless to the organization if they are not willing to work hard using their powers, abilities, and abilities. This motivation is essential because, with reason, it is hoped that every individual employee will be willing to work hard and enthusiastically to achieve high productivity.

Harold Koontz in Hasibuan (2007: 95) mentions **Motivation refers to the drive and effort to satisfy a want or goal.** Motivation refers to the impulse and endeavors to fulfill a need or a plan. Hasibuan (2007:95) posits: Motivation is the provision of the driving force that creates a person's passion for work. They are willing to work together, work effectively, and integrate with all their efforts to achieve satisfaction. American Encyclopedia in Hasibuan (2007:96):

Motivation: That predisposition (the subject of much controversy) within the individual arouses sustains and directs his behavior. Basis involves such factors as biological and emotional needs that can only be inferred from observation conduct.

Motivation is a tendency (a trait that is the subject of opposition) in a person that evokes and directs his actions. Motivation includes factors of biological and emotional needs that can only be suspected from the observation of human behavior. Zein, Badudu (2001: 909) mentions that motivation is the intention, motivation, the basis for doing something; there is an earnest effort to achieve good results. Luthans (2002:249) says that:

"Motivation is a process that starts from physical and psychic deficiencies or needs that contribute to behaviors or impulses aimed at achieving organizational goals."

So what is meant by motivation is the driving force that results in a member of the organization willing and willing to exert abilities in the form of expertise or skills, energy, and time to organize various activities that are his responsibility and fulfill his obligations, to achieve the goals and multiple goals of the organization that have been predetermined.

Early Theories About Motivation

The theory of motivation begins with the four early theories of motivation of Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory, McGregor's Theory X and Y's Theory of Two Factors Herzberg, and McClelland's theory of three conditions. Although more recent explanations of motivation have been developed, these early theories are critical because they are the basis of the contemporary ideas of motivation set. There are still many managers who use them.

Maslow's Theory of Hierarchy of Needs

The most famous theory of motivation is probably the *hierarchy of needs theory* of Abraham Maslow. Maslow was a psychologist who stated that in each person, there is a hierarchy of five conditions:

1. **Physiological needs:** A person's need for food and drink, shelter, sex, and other physical conditions.
2. **Safety needs** A person's need for security and protection from physical and emotional crimes and the assurance that physical needs will continue to be met.
3. **Social needs:** A person's need for affection, belonging, and friendship. **Esteem needs** A person's need for internal reward factors, such as self-esteem, autonomy, and achievement, and external reward factors, such as status, recognition, and attention.
4. **Self-actualization needs:** A person's need for growth, the achievement of one's potential, and self-fulfillment: the drive to be able to become what one wants (Robbins and Coulter 2016).

Maslow argued that each level in the hierarchy of needs must be substantially met before the next need becomes dominant. An individual moves upon a hierarchy of needs from one level to the next. (Figure 1.1) In addition, Maslow separates the five needs into higher and lower classes. Figure

Figure 1: Maslow's Level of Needs

Source: Robbins and Judge (2017)

McGregor's Theory X and Y Theory

Douglas McGregor is best known for putting forward two assumptions about the human nature of Theory X and Theory Y. Simply put; Theory X is a negative view of people who assume that workers have little ambition, do not like work, evade responsibility, and need to be strictly controlled to work effectively. Theory Y is an optimistic view that assumes that employees enjoy the work of seeking and accepting responsibility and practicing self-direction. McGregor believes that the assumptions of Theory Y should be a guide for management practitioners and states that participation in decision-making, challenging and responsible work and good group relationships will maximize employee motivation.

Unfortunately, there is no evidence to convince us that any assumptions apply or that being a manager of Theory Y is the only way to motivate the employees; for example, Jen-Hsun Huang, founder of Nvidia Corporation (Robbins and Coulter 2016). An innovative and successful manufacturer of microchips has used convincing hugs and intense love to motivate its employees. However, he is also intolerant of chaos. He allegedly targeted a project team at one meeting because the group tended to repeat mistakes. "Do you suck? He asked his stunned employee. "Because if you suck, get up and say that you suck. " The message conveyed in the classical style of Theory X is that if indeed you need help, then ask for it. Although rude, in this case, the approach worked because employees came to know that they had to take responsibility for the mistakes and figure out how to deal with them.

Two-Factor Theory of Herzberg

Frederick Herzberg's two-factor theory (also called the motivational theory of hygiene-hygiene theory) proposes that intrinsic factors are related to job satisfaction. In contrast, extrinsic characteristics are related to job dissatisfaction (McShane and Glinow 2018). Herzberg wanted to know when someone felt very comfortable (satisfied) or not yet dissatisfied with their work. He concluded that people's answers when they feel pleased with their work are significantly different from their answers when they feel uncomfortable.

Specific characteristics consistently have to do with job satisfaction (factors on the left side) and others with job dissatisfaction (factors on the right side). When people are comfortable with their work, they mention intrinsic factors arising from work, such as achievements, recognition, and responsibilities. On the other hand, when they feel dissatisfied, they tend to say extrinsic actor factors arising from the work context, such as company policy and administration, supervision, interpersonal relationships, and working conditions.

In addition, Herzberg believes the data shows that the opposite of satisfaction is not discontent, as has always been accepted. Removing unsatisfactory characteristics from a job does not necessarily make the job more satisfying (or motivating). As shown in Figure 3, Herzberg states that there is a double continuum that arises: The opposite of

Figure *satisfaction (satisfaction)* is "not satisfaction (*no satisfaction*)," and the opposite of "dissatisfaction (dissatisfaction)" is "not dissatisfaction (no dissatisfaction)."

Figure 0: Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory**Figure 3: Comparing Views of Satisfaction and Dissatisfaction****F-Factors of Actors Affecting Performance**

According to Robert L. Mathis and John H. Jackson (2001:82), the factors influencing the workforce's performance are 1. Their abilities, 2. Motivation, 3. The support received 4. The existence of the work they do, and 5. Their relationship with the organization.

Mangkunegara (2000) states that factors that affect performance include: a. Ability factors Psychologically, employees' ability consists of potential ability (IQ) and reality ability (education). Therefore, employees need to be placed in a job by their expertise. b. Motivational factors Motivation is formed from an employee's attitude (attitude) in dealing with work situations (*situation*). Motivation is a condition that moves employees directional toward achieving work goals. A mental attitude is a mental state that encourages a person to strive to achieve maximum work potential.

Indicators and Premises of Human Resource Performance

Assessment/measurement of performance needs to be carried out to determine whether, during the implementation of performance, there is a deviation from the predetermined plan, whether the performance can be carried out according to a predetermined schedule, or whether the performance results have been achieved as expected. John L. Hradesky (1995:237-238) gives the criteria of performance-oriented individuals.

Table 1: Criteria Performance

No	Criteria indicator	Definition
1	Intellectual abilities	Capacity to work actively and tirelessly. This is a tendency to express positive behavior.
2	Assertiveness	Analyze possibilities and commit to a definite choice quickly or briefly.
3	The spirit of enthusiasm	The capacity to think logically.
4	Results-oriented	Desire is intrinsic and is committed to achieving an outcome and completing what has been started by it.
5	Maturity	Proper attitude and behavior. An ability to exercise emotional control and self-discipline.
6	Assertive	An ability to take over responsibility.
7	Interpersonal skills	Friendly, quick to respond, and emphasize everyone to give a response. A tendency to pay attention to and show awareness, understanding, and concern for the feelings of others.
8	Openness	The ability to express opinions and feelings honestly, as they

No	Criteria indicator	Definition
		are, and be direct.
9	Curiosity	An ability to make complex efforts objectively and briefly. Critically assess an event or person.
10	Proactive	The ability to carry out own initiatives, anticipate problems, and accept responsibility in carrying out work.
11	Capability empowerment	The ability to trust and give hope, guidance, and authority to others to carry out their respective responsibilities.
12	Technical	Knowledge, skills, decisions, behaviors, and responsibilities.

Source: John L. Hradesky (1995:237-238)

The indicators regarding the performance of human resources are as follows: 1) intellectual ability, 2) assertiveness, 3) the spirit of enthusiasm, 4) result-oriented, 5) maturity, 6) assertiveness, 7) interpersonal skills, 8) openness, 9) curiosity, 10) proactive, 11) empowerment of abilities and 12) technical.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methods used in this study are broadly divided into 2 (two) ways. The first research method is descriptive; the second method is a method using verifiable analysis.

1. **Descriptive statistics:** statistics that discuss ways of presenting data through tables and graphs and processing data to determine the size of centering and dispersion so that it becomes information.

2. **Inference statistics or inductive statistics:** statistics that discuss ways of inference about populations. Hypothesis: the process of concluding inductively, that is, analyzing the data obtained from the sample so that several statistics are obtained that are used to estimate parameters and test hypotheses about the value of a particular parameter, the difference between two or more parameters, as well as the causality linkage between two or more variables applicable to population.

This study consists of six variables, namely, four free variables, one intervening variable, and one bound variable.

As for the dependent variable in this study, it is:

1. Motivation (X). As for the theory that underlies it, it uses the idea of the American Encyclopedia in Hasibuan (2007:96), with its indicators as follows: 1) Needs, 2) Desires, 3) Achievements, 4) Work itself, 5) Compensation.

2. Human Resource Performance (Y). As for the theory that underlies it, using the idea of Robert L. Mathis and John H. Jackson, Diana Angelica (2006:112), with the following indicators: 1) Intellectual ability, 2) Assertiveness, 3) The spirit of enthusiasm, 4) Oriented results, 5) Maturity, 6) Assertive, 7) Interpersonal skills, 8) Openness, 9) Curiosity, 10) Proactive, 11) Empowerment of abilities, 12) Technical.

In this study, the operationalization of variables aims to explain the indictment of the indicators used to measure research variables, both independent variables, intervening variables, and dependent variables. The scaling technique used to calculate the research variables' thunders is the Likert Scale. The Likert scale measures a person's attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of social phenomena.

According to Sugiono (2010: 107), this social phenomenon has been established explicitly by researchers in research, referred to as a research variable. The measured variable is described with the variable indicator with the Likert scale. The indicator is used as a starting point to compile instrument items that can be statements or questions.

A grade rating indicates a relative order of assessment or level of preference. The operationalization of variables in this study also establishes the variables studied. After providing the variables learned, research instruments can be compiled (in this thing is a questionnaire). Research instruments in social affairs and management that have been standardized are challenging to find. For this reason, researchers must be able to make instruments that will be used in research. The starting point of the drafting is the research variables set to be researched. These variables are given their operational definitions, and then the indicator is determined. This indicator then describes it into items of question or statement.

The variables to be studied, which are reflected in identifying the problem, the chart of the research framework, or the formulation of hypotheses, must subsequently be operationalized so that the variables can be measured appropriately, based on the indicators that make them up.

Table 2: Operationalization of Variables

Variable	Concept of Variables	Indicator	Scale
Motivation	That predisposition (itself the subject of much controversy) within the individual arouses, sustains, and directs his behavior. Motivation involves such factors as biological and emotional needs that can only be inferred from observation of behavior. American Encyclopedia in Hasibuan (2007:96)	Necessity	Ordinal
		Desire	Ordinal
		Achievement	Ordinal
		The work itself	Ordinal
		Compensation	Ordinal
Human Resource Performance	"Performance is the performance of functions required of an act, an achievement, a public exhibition of skills. Performance is a condition that must be known and confirmed to certain parties to determine the level of achievement of the results of an agency connected with the vision carried out by an organization or company and know the positive and negative impact of an operational policy." Robert L. Mathis dan John H. Jackson terjemahan Diana Angelica (2006:112)	Intellectual abilities.	Ordinal
		Assertiveness.	Ordinal
		The spirit of enthusiasm.	Ordinal
		Results-oriented.	Ordinal
		Maturity.	Ordinal
		Assertive,	Ordinal
		Interpersonal skills.	Ordinal
		Openness.	Ordinal
		Curiosity.	Ordinal
		Proactive.	Ordinal
		We are empowering abilities.	Ordinal
		Technical.	Ordinal

Population and Research Samples

This study used sample data from the specified population consisting of auditors at the ITJEN Kemendikbudristek in 4 parts. Based on population characteristics, the technique taken from this sampling is to use the **Cluster Random Sampling** technique.

In determining the data taken from the sources that are the object of the study, the population, and samples that describe the research area and the representation of each region. Cooper and Schindler (2011) that a population constitutes the sum of whole or whole groups, events, or things of interest for researchers to investigate.

The researcher selected the Cluster Random Sampling sampling technique based on the characteristics of the population divided based on the group sections in the ITJEN kemendikbudristek. This sampling technique did not cause a loss of features and variations in each group (**cluster**) that became the study population.

Data Analysis

The data analysis technique of this research uses two analyses. **The first analysis is descriptive.** Using descriptive investigation provides an overview of respondents' perceptions of the variables studied. **The second is verifiable analysis**, which aims to conduct hypothesis testing through statistical testing. Through these two data analysis techniques, it is hoped that they will obtain simple conclusions (generalizations) regarding the complete (comprehensive) causality linkage.

Individual test to determine the meaningfulness or significance of each path coefficient by using cr test statistics. Statistical testing using the Lisrel program using cr. Cr statistics are identified with the t-test statistics revealed by Ferdinand cited by Kusnendi (2006: 89). Therefore cr is calculated to equal the t-test based on the formula:

$$Cr_{ij} = \frac{\rho_{ij}}{SE} = \frac{\rho_{ij}}{\sqrt{\frac{(1-R_i^2)C_{jj}}{n-k-1}}}$$

Where:

ρ_{ij} = The path coefficient (which has not been stabilized) between *exogenous* variables against *endogenous* variables contained in the analyzed model,

SE = Standard *error* path coefficient obtained for the analyzed model

n = Sample size,

k = The number of *exogenous* variables analyzed

C_{jj} = Elements of the inverse matrix of the correlation of *exogenous* variables of the analyzed model.

This test is used to determine the validity of the path value against the dependent variable (Y). suppose the path is insignificant (P-count < the error rate), then the course must be discarded, and the new way recalculated. The above cr result must have a P-count value < an error degree with a value of 0.01, then H_0 is rejected, and an alternative hypothesis of H_1 is accepted. For each of the ideas above, then tested with hypothesis tests, the level of significance used is 1%.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of the description of the level of motivation was obtained from the dissemination of questionnaires regarding the cause. Based on the results of a descriptive study using a psychological scale, the following results are obtained:

Table03: Motivation Level

Levels	Frequency	Percentage
Tall	8	25,81%
Keep	13	41,94%
Low	10	32,26%
Total	31	100,00%

Based on the calculation results, it is known that the motivation level of 41.94% is in the medium category while 32.26% is in a low sort. The condition suggests that motivation is a force that exists in the individual; it's not their actual behavior. Thus, direction, intensity, and persistence are cognitive (thought) and emotional states that directly cause employees to move as expected.

The level of employee performance based on the results of questionnaire measurements based on intellectual appearance, affirmation, emanate enthusiasm, ber orientation on the results, kedewasaan, an excellent, interpersonal skills, openness, kingintahuan, proactive, pemberdayaan ability, and the ability of tennis.

Table04: Employee Performance Levels

Levels	Frequency	Percentage
Tall	7	22,58%

Levels	Frequency	Percentage
Keep	15	48,39%
Low	9	29,03%
Total	31	100,00%

Referring to the results of the descriptive analysis, it is known that the employee performance level of 48.39% is in the medium category, and 29.03% is in the low sort. High performance shows the ability of employees to carry out their roles in the organization is high. Meanwhile, poor performance shows that the power of employees to carry out their functions is not as expected.

Path Analysis

Figure 04: Path Analysis.

Based on the analysis, it is known that the value of the path coefficient is 0.821, with the value of the effectiveness level of the model of 67.4%. The value indicates that the level of motivation will impact employee performance. High and low motivation will positively affect employees' high and low performance. The Cr value is 7,877. The value indicates the research hypothesis is accepted where the high and low motivation will determine the high and quiet performance.

High low motivation indicates employees' increased willingness to carry out their roles in the organization. The higher the level of motivation, it illustrates the high level of readiness of employees to carry out their functions, continuously improving their ability to carry out roles in the organization properly.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion, it can be concluded that the level of motivation and employee performance is not optimal. As for statistical analysis, it is known that the level of motivation has a positive and significant influence in carrying out its role in the organization.

The suggestion from the results of this study is that the fragrance of increasing the level of motivation at the ITJEN of the Ministry of Education and Culture must continue to be improved. By fulfilling all the needs expected by employees in supporting their work activities. Fulfilling all the requirements of employees in supporting their work activities will increase the willingness of employees to carry out their roles. A high level of readiness will improve employees' ability to carry out their functions.

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